

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Challenges in Science Journalism: the Dutch and Flemish media landscape case study

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Samenvatting

Semigestructureerd interviews met zes Nederlandse en Vlaamse wetenschapsjournalisten brachten vijf hoofdthema's van huidige en toekomstige werkvelduitdagingen aan het licht: **economische zekerheid, inhoud, werkomgeving, wetenschapsrelaties** en **politiek en samenleving**. Belangrijke zorgen zijn lage inkomens, werkdruk, tijdsdruk, beïnvloeding door wetenschapsinstututen, polarisatie en misinformatie. Verwachte toekomstige uitdagingen zijn concurrentie van wetenschapscommunicatoren en generatieve AI, die de relevantie van wetenschapsjournalisten in gevaar kunnen brengen.

Abstract

This research project explores the current and expected future challenges faced by science journalists working in the Netherlands and Flanders, drawing on semi-structured interviews with six professionals from both regions. Thematic analysis of the interviews resulted in five overarching challenge themes: **economic security, content, work environment, relationships with scientists, and politics and society**. Key concerns from participants included limited income, high workloads, increasing time pressure, scientists and science institutes controlling science reporting, and political and societal developments such as polarization on scientific topics and the spread of misinformation. New threats for science journalists such as competition from science communicators and generative AI were mentioned as potential future challenges, as they could impact their professional relevance and content forms. These findings both support and expand on international literature and can contribute to policy discussions regarding the protection of the independence and societal role of science journalists in the Dutch and Flemish media landscape.

Author guidelines

The main author guidelines were followed from het *Tijdschrift voor Communicatiewetenschap* (Journal for Communication Science), which is a journal that publishes articles regarding the developments within the communication sciences

(e.g. journalism) in the Netherlands and Flanders. To publish in this journal, a research article should have a maximum word count of 6000 words (including references), a summary in Dutch (max. 60 words), and an abstract in English (max. 150 words, including title in English and five key words). For the references, the journal's editors employ APA (7th edition). With permission of my supervisor, I exceeded the maximum word count.

Introduction

Science communicators play a crucial role in bridging the gap between complex scientific research and public understanding. In this time of rapid technological advancements, new health crises, and pressing environmental challenges, the demand for accurate, accessible, and – perhaps even more important – engaging science communication has never been more critical (Molina & Abadal, 2025).

Science communication can be defined by the goals it aims to achieve. First of all, science communicators aim to increase the overall awareness and understanding of science, thereby awakening a public interest in scientific topics, making people more confident to talk about and engage in science-related matters (Burns et al., 2003). Moreover, science communication also enables the general public, science practitioners, and every professional between these worlds to have more effective and meaningful interactions, as it provides their audiences with useful scientific skills, media, activities, and dialogues (Burns et al., 2003).

One of the key players in the world of science communication is the science journalist (Dijkstra et al., 2024). One of the tasks of science journalists is to serve as intermediaries, interpreting hard-to-grasp scientific developments and findings, and transforming it into digestible – and entertaining – stories to be read by the general public. As McCombs & Shaw found in their study from 1972, science journalism not only informs and educates the layman, but also impacts the public opinion about science-related topics, influences policy decisions, and shapes how overall society reacts to scientific issues, and this continues to be the case in the current decade (Van Dam et al., 2020).

Science journalism is also present in the broad media landscape of the Netherlands and Flanders. In this Dutch-speaking region, most professionals working in journalism work either in full-time employment or as freelancers (Hanitzsch et al., 2019). It is estimated that the Netherlands counts around 18500 journalists (NVJ Arbeidsmarktmonitor, 2024) and Flanders around 2600 journalists (VVJ-Jaarverslag 2024, 2024), although it is not precisely known what fraction of those specialize in science news. Those that do focus on science reporting work for newspapers, such as *de Volkskrant* and *De Standaard*, for magazines like *KIJK*, science TV programs such as *Focus*, or for online platforms like *NEMO Kennislink*.

Recent political developments in the Netherlands have underscored the importance of reporting about the current situation in the world of science. By the end of 2024, the former Dutch government announced to implement significant financial cutbacks regarding scientific research and higher education. As scientific institutes could be struggling with reduced funding, science journalists must perform the crucial task of highlighting the consequences of such cuts and maintaining the public engagement with science.

Although the work of science journalists is an important part in engaging the Dutch and Belgian public with science, modern developments challenge these very professions. Internet and social media have disrupted the traditional news model of news agencies having a monopoly in disseminating (science) news. This disruption has led to budget cuts and reduced resources for specialized reporting such as science journalism (Dunwoody, 2021). As of 2016, 63 out of 100 Dutch science journalists questioned for a nation-wide survey said to be working mainly as freelancer, having no permanent employing contract with any news agency (Korthagen, 2016). Simultaneously, the spread of misinformation and the politicization and polarization of some scientific topics, such as global warming, may also have complicated the tasks of science journalists, as they now need to be more cautious with the sources they use.

While these broader themes are recognized as influential factors in science news reporting, a comprehensive overview of the specific challenges faced by Dutch and Flemish science journalists remains to be made. An overview of this kind could yield insights into how to develop effective policies to support science journalists conducting their work, both now and in the future. This exploratory study aims to create the basis for such an overview of challenges based on interviews that have been conducted with Dutch and Flemish professionals working in the field of science journalism.

Challenges in science journalism

On a global scale, multiple studies into science journalism have touched upon or explored the challenges these professionals encounter in their work. These studies, often involving surveys and interviews with science journalists, have provided valuable insights into the field's current state and obstacles. The following sections will quickly go over the most prevalent challenges discussed in current literature. An overview of all challenges found in these recent studies is depicted in Table 1.

The workload is too high

Five studies discussing science journalism mention the high workload as one of the main challenges that science news reporters face, as well as one of the main factors causing further obstacles in their work (see Table 1 for references). One explanation for this increase in workload could be the lay-offs of fulltime contracted science journalists that have occurred in the last decades (Dunwoody, 2021). Effectively, this decrease in science journalism capacity has only worsened the stress on the professionals still working in the field (Ashwell, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020). Additionally, the expansion of the online environment and social media has also led to the demand that science news reporters become more skilled in the diverse production of multimedia content, such as video and podcasts, requiring them to adjust nearly every single story for different media outlets (Maiden et al., 2020; Murcott & Williams, 2013). Lastly, exhaustive reporting of one single scientific topic due to public interest, such as in the case of the COVID-19 pandemic, was also once mentioned as being a great burden on the work capacity of science journalists (Massarani et al., 2021).

Table 1: Challenges faced by science journalists according to current literature. Ordered with regard to frequency of publications mentioning the challenge.

Challenge faced by science journalists	Publications mentioning challenge
Workload too high	(Ashwell, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Massarani et al., 2021; Murcott & Williams, 2013; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Financial matters	(Dijkstra et al., 2024; Korthagen, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Difficult communication with scientists	(Ashwell, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Nguyen & Tran, 2019; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Increased time pressure	(Dijkstra et al., 2024; Dunwoody, 2021; Maiden et al., 2020; Murcott & Williams, 2013)
Forced to use preprints and PR materials	(Ashwell, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Massarani et al., 2021; Murcott & Williams, 2013)
Work is desk-bound	(Ashwell, 2016; Massarani et al., 2021; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Fake news and misinformation	(Allan, 2011; Dunwoody, 2021; Massarani et al., 2021)
Science reporting lacks prestige	(Ashwell, 2016; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Editors undervalue science reporting	(Nguyen & Tran, 2019; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Aggressive PR industry	(Ashwell, 2016; Murcott & Williams, 2013)
Multilingual countries complicate targeting	(Dijkstra et al., 2024; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Lack of (journalistic) training	(Dunwoody, 2021; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Lack of scientific expertise	(Maiden et al., 2020; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Scientists directly reach audiences	(Brüggemann et al., 2020; Dunwoody, 2021)
Other parties influence science news	(Nguyen & Tran, 2019; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Lack of local experts/research/publications	(Dijkstra et al., 2024; Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Forced to become freelancers	(Dunwoody, 2021; Korthagen, 2016)
Balancing journalism and institutional work	(Dunwoody, 2021; Korthagen, 2016)
Slow developments conflict with news criteria	(Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Obtaining data from external parties	(Qusien & Robbins, 2024)
Building credibility as freelancer	(Dunwoody, 2021)
Shared sources complicate original stories	(Maiden et al., 2020)
Reaching specific audiences	(Maiden et al., 2020)
Heavy reliance on foreign sources	(Nguyen & Tran, 2019)
Lack of favorable copyright conditions	(Korthagen, 2016)
Balancing professional relationships and independence	(Korthagen, 2016)
Rising demand for multimedia skills	(Murcott & Williams, 2013)

Overall, this increase in work demand has led to science journalists having less time and space available to write original and in-depth stories, forcing them to only cover the biggest topics (Ashwell, 2016; Korthagen, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Qusien &

Robbins, 2024), and has also led to many of the other challenges highlighted in the following sections.

Financial matters

Studied science journalists often state that little money is available for their work, both in the form of funding and salary. One of the interviewees of Maiden et al. (2020) even stated the situation as directly as “everybody is being squeezed”. The lack of pay can be explained by the decreased readership of traditionally dominant newspapers and magazines, which has resulted in less fundings and lost interest from advertisers. Furthermore, audiences have become more reluctant to pay for news with the abundance of free news online (Dijkstra et al., 2024). Studies involving environmental science news reporters in Pakistan even found that some were forced to use their own resources, as editors would not financially support their original stories (Qusien & Robbins, 2024). Though this case from Pakistan might be an extreme on the global level, a study among Dutch science journalists from 2016 did find that these professionals were also worried about the decreasing rates they receive for their journalistic work (Korthagen, 2016).

Communication with scientists is becoming difficult or inefficient

To create new stories, science journalists need to contact sources, which are often scientists. Hence, having easy access to and maintaining good relationships with researchers is essential for a smooth working experience. Yet, easy and efficient communication with scientists is not always straightforward. Reach-out and communication with scientists is especially difficult for science journalists in the Global South due to scientists not trusting journalists, failing cooperation from the science community, and a general lack of local experts (Nguyen & Tran, 2019; Qusien & Robbins, 2024). However, also in the wealthier regions, such as in New-Zealand and Europe, science journalists are not immune to difficulties in the communication with scientists. The communication between journalists and scientists can be hampered by both parties lacking time to interact extensively, and by journalists not having enough time and resources to perform self-research to level with the scientific experts (Maiden et al., 2020). Furthermore, instances have been documented where designated contact persons, frequently scientists, listed on scientific press releases were not easily available for interviews, resulting in frustrations among science journalists operating under strict publishing deadlines (Ashwell, 2016).

The time pressure has increased

More people read and watch their news primarily on the internet. Around half of Dutch (47%) and Belgian (51%) people report to use the internet and social media as their main source for news (Digital News Report Nederland 2024, 2024). Science journalists are expected to work at a faster pace to keep up with online demand. The experienced increase in deadlines and corresponding time pressures has been identified as a general trend among science journalists worldwide (Dijkstra et al., 2024; Maiden et al., 2020; Murcott & Williams, 2013). Sharon Dunwoody (2021) accurately explains this trend:

Building science news stories for Internet consumption presents many challenges, among them the need for constant updating, managing the speed with which information must be turned into narrative and maximizing the brevity of those narratives, so critical to audiences who will devote only seconds to a story. (p. 27)

Again, this challenge can be coupled to the increase in workload in science journalism, as a growing amount of work now competes for the same amount of time a journalist has during their working hours.

Science journalists feel forced to use public relations materials and preprints

One of the consequences of the increasing lack of time and resources is that science journalists feel the need to apply easier and faster sources to use for their stories. Some smaller news agencies have been reported to have so little staff and resources to cover science news that they often literally take over public relations (PR) materials, such as press releases, on their platforms. Larger news platforms generally are less yielding towards the usage of PR materials and keep up their work as independent bringers of scientific news (Ashwell, 2016). In this way, they avoid becoming so-called “churnalists”, where journalists succumb to time pressures and are forced to “churn out” science stories brought and framed by PR professionals from research institutes, thereby becoming a direct mouthpiece of those institutes. Moreover, such practices might also be harmful to the scientific community itself, as science may face a potential erosion of credibility due to insufficient external criticism (Murcott & Williams, 2013).

Also the use of preprint material (i.e. publications before the peer review process has concluded) has been occurring more often, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, when a lot of research was performed at a much faster pace than was previously the case. To keep up with this pace, science journalists were at times pressured into less critical reporting and hence using more non-peer-reviewed publications (Massarani et al., 2021), although journalists in general continue to be extra cautious when using such preprints (Maiden et al., 2020).

Fake news and misinformation

Another result of the increase in internet usage is the more common occurrence of misinformation. Also science topics, often politically polarizing, have fallen subject to fake news (West & Bergstrom, 2021). In search of reliable sources, science journalists need to deal with these kinds of misinformation as well, sifting through the vast quantities of information available online and discarding nonfactual sources (Allan, 2011; Dunwoody, 2021). The circulation of fake science stories also adds a potential new task to the workload of science journalists: fact-checking. This practice mostly entails checking information with known experts, consulting fake-news-tracking websites, and cross-checking information using a variety of sources (Massarani et al., 2021), all taking up work time from science journalists.

All in all, several challenges that science journalists face during their work have been identified by previous research, albeit on a global level. Despite these efforts, similar research into the Dutch-speaking media landscape of the Netherlands and Flanders remains to be conducted. To bridge this gap, this research aims to answer the research question: *What are the challenges Dutch and Flemish science journalists are currently facing during their work?* Additionally, a future perspective can also be obtained, hopefully answering the second research question: *What new challenges do Dutch and Flemish science journalists expect to be facing during their work within the coming ten years?*

Theoretical framework

Given the multitude of different challenges confronting science journalists, it is sensible to employ a theoretical framework to categorize these diverse issues. A potent framework is the Hierarchy of Influences model as proposed by Shoemaker and Reese (1996), which postulates that there are five levels of influences forming media content,

increasing from micro to macro scales: the individual, routine, organizational, institutional, and social system level. As the developers have argued that the model still holds in the current, highly networked, digital media landscape (Reese & Shoemaker, 2016), it can be attempted to subdivide the challenges faced by science journalists in these same five levels, making for a more robust overview.

Some of the challenges mentioned in literature can also be categorized following this model, to give an impression of what such a subdivision could look like. For example, the individual level entails problems such as the science journalist lacking decent journalistic training or having not enough expertise to cover certain science topics. The routine level is more about the challenges within the daily work life of the journalists, such as the increased workloads and time pressures. Going up a level, the organization the journalist works in can have a negative influence as well, such as editors prioritizing other kinds of reporting (e.g. politics or economy) over science reporting, and media owners or advertisers influencing the contents of published science news. The institutional level indicates everything outside the organization, from PR professionals pushing their agendas, to governments not funding science news. The highest level is that of the social system, which contains the total dynamics within society. Factors from this level that challenge science journalists are characteristics of the journalists' country, such as the existence of two or more official languages, and social developments such as the rise of the internet and misinformation.

Methods

This study employed a qualitative approach using semi-structured interviews to explore the challenges faced by Dutch and Flemish science journalists. This method allowed for a broad, though in-depth, exploration of participants' experiences and challenges, while also staying focused on the topics relevant for the research (Croucher & Cronn-Mills, 2022).

Interviews

Participating science journalists were recruited from various media outlets in the Netherlands and Flanders by means of purposive sampling. A total of eight science journalists were approached, from which six agreed to participate in this study. The aim was to achieve a relatively fair balance between gender and nationality among

participants, which was moderately successful with four men and two women participating, four of which were Dutch and two Flemish (Table 2). This study falls under the Umbrella Ethical Approval as provided by the Science Communication and Society department of Leiden University. Before the interviews, all participants were provided with general research information, an informed consent form that they all signed (Appendix 1), and the main questions covered during the interview. Questions were sent beforehand such that participants would already be able to think about the challenges they experience in their work and would not be caught off guard during the interview.

An interview guide was prepared that focused on the challenges in science journalism that participants experience and on their expectations of what new challenges may arise in the near future (Appendix 2). An introductory question was always posed to the participants to describe a typical working day to get more insight in their work life, as well as to break the ice. The questions regarding current challenges and expected future challenges were always prompted with follow-up questions asking specifically for challenges they encounter on the different levels of the Hierarchy of Influences model by Shoemaker and Reese (1996). These prompts effectively provided the participants with new angles towards answering the question, which often lead to the participants coming up with new themes.

The semi-structured interviews took place in the period between 31 March and 9 April 2025 and were conducted in Dutch, either face-to-face at a place convenient to the participant or via Zoom, depending on the participants' availability and location. Interviews lasted between 17 and 41 minutes with a mean duration of 30 min. All interviews were recorded and transcribed using the online Good Tape transcription software and manual correction. Dutch transcripts were translated to English using the translation tool from Microsoft Word and manually checked afterwards by a native Dutch speaker. Roughly 20 percent of the translated transcripts were double-checked by a second native speaker to ensure the correctness of the used translation method.

Table 2: Precise description of occupation, nationality, and gender of the six science journalists interviewed.

Participant	Occupation	Nationality	Gender
SJ1	Freelance science journalist	Dutch	Male
SJ2	Freelance science journalist	Flemish-Belgian	Male
SJ3	Science editor national newspaper	Dutch	Male

SJ4	Freelance science journalist	Dutch	Male
SJ5	Editor science magazine	Flemish-Belgian	Female
SJ6	Editor science TV program	Dutch	Female

Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis was performed on the translated transcripts using Atlas.ti software. This method allowed for the identification of recurring themes and challenges across the interview data set (Braun & Clarke, 2012). Themes and subthemes regarding the different challenges emerged inductively from the interview transcripts and were systematically coded. A codebook (Appendix 3) was constructed and refined through an iterative process of discussions between researcher and supervisor. Transcript sections relevant to this study were highlighted, and every section was coded for two topics: 1. the challenge mentioned and, 2. the moment of the challenge mentioned (current challenge or expected future challenge). To check for intercoder reliability, a second student coded 21% of all transcripts following the same codebook. For the coded challenges and the coded moments of challenges, percent agreements of 88% and 95% were found, respectively. Both agreement percentages were deemed high enough and analysis of the coded data was continued.

Lastly, all found challenges were inductively categorized in different challenge themes, and these categories were compared to the Hierarchy of Influences model. This framework helped structuring the found challenges across different levels, from the individual to societal system level.

Interview results

From the six interviews, a multitude of different challenges emerged. By solely focusing on the challenge types that were mentioned by at least half ($n \geq 3$) of the interviewed science journalists, a selection of frequently mentioned challenges remained (Figure 1). This selection could be divided over five overarching challenge themes: **economic security**, **content**, **work environment**, **relationships with scientists**, and **politics and society**.

Figure 1: Main challenges mentioned by science journalists participating in this study. Numbers between brackets indicate how many of the participants ($N = 6$) mentioned the corresponding challenge.

Economic security

The one theme that all participants talked about at some point during their interviews was that of maintaining **economic security**, which the International Committee of the Red Cross defines as ‘the condition of individuals, households or communities to be able to cover their essential needs and unavoidable expenditures in a sustainable and dignified manner, given physiological requirements, the environments and prevailing cultural standards’ (Economic Security Strategy 2020-2023, 2020). Generating or – in the case of the editors – offering a steady *income* has proven to be a challenge for each interviewed science journalist, often because there is a *limited amount of work and clients available*. As economic security is predominantly a personal issue, the Hierarchy of Influences model would classify these challenges under the individual and organizational level (Figure 2), although the problem of editors not having enough resources to provide for their freelancers could also be classified as organizational.

All freelancing science journalists mentioned that it is occasionally hard to financially get by in their profession, as they feel that there is only a *limited amount of clients and work available* for all freelancers. As one of them put it:

In science journalism, by definition, it is almost a bit of an uncertain existence. Sometimes you won't mind that at all, but I can also imagine that at some point it will work against you a bit more, because it's just not a very big field. There are not a lot of clients, there are not a lot of publications. (SJ4)

Furthermore, they clearly showed dissatisfaction with the compensations they received at times for the assignments they did obtain. The former participant described these low payments to be because of the small budgets, as “there are (...) simply fewer readers.” (SJ4) To ensure a reliable *income*, the freelancers often had to take on other side jobs, such as teaching at universities (SJ1+SJ4) or accepting copywriting work for science institutes (SJ2). All three science editors interviewed also admitted that budgetary tightness within their organizations frequently limited their ability to employ as many freelancing journalists as they would have liked. Especially the editor for the science TV program (SJ6) was afraid whether her job would continue to exist in the coming years, as her employer, a Dutch public broadcaster, had just been announced to be discontinued due to governmental budgetary cuts. Moreover, the national newspaper's science editor-in-chief underscored the importance of being able to pay a fair price to their freelancers: “It is time-consuming work. It is human work. You can't robotize this or anything. (...) And then also with people who can do something. So that's just expensive (...) to make.” (SJ3) If salaries remained too low, he was concerned, freshly graduated university students might not consider science journalism as a serious career possibility, which could in turn erode the profession over time.

Figure 2: Schematic comparison of Shoemaker and Reese's Hierarchy of Influences model (2016) to the overarching challenge themes found in this study. Specific challenges are shown on the different levels of the model and can occur on different levels. Visualization is inspired by a similar representation by Engesser (2017).

Content

At its core, the main product that science journalists deliver is the science news **content** they create. Most science journalists interviewed for this study focused mainly on the production of written content (SJ1-SJ5), although one of the interviewees was exclusively involved in the making of a science news TV program (SJ6). Regarding this theme, the main challenge they mentioned was the necessity to innovate their scientific journalistic content creation, both by making more *creative and engaging content* and using more *multimedia content*. The interviewees often reasoned that this need for innovation to be a direct result from the current rise and *impact of AI* usage, and expected this trend to aggravate in the coming years. Following the Hierarchy of Influences Model, content-related challenges fall in the routine level, as it applies to the everyday work of the journalist, while the impact of AI is more related to the overall social system (Figure 2).

Recently, the societal impact of artificial intelligence has become increasingly visible, a development that has not gone unnoticed by the science journalists interviewed for this study. When asked for their expected future challenges, interviewees commonly discussed the likely *impact of AI* on their current and future work. One of the

participants contemplated how the public might perceive science journalists in a media landscape dominated by AI-fabricated content:

I think one challenge that's already starting to play out is those automatically generated texts (...) I'm not directly afraid that they will replace us, but I'm a bit afraid of the fact that people think they *could* replace us. (...) That we will be seen as even less useful as we are seen now. We are already seen as some kind of luxury product and I think that feeling will get worse. (SJ5)

Another was concerned that, with automated content creators on the rise, “the bar will be much higher for the regular messages. If you just write generic messages, you will be outcompeted.” (SJ2) The pressure to come up with novel ways of presenting science news clearly is something on the mind of the Dutch and Flemish science journalist, as almost all (except SJ5) talked at some point about the challenges they face in their attempts to make their content more *creative and engaging* and *multimedia*-based. Participants mentioned various ways to achieve these criteria, such as having to “find your own voice” (SJ2), involving more “the human aspect” of science news (SJ4), or – in the case of the science TV program editor – making sure that the content is visually pleasing to watch (SJ6). One acknowledged that he and his colleagues could perhaps learn a great deal from social media content creators to attract younger audiences, because “those tiktokkers (...) just talk to their audience in a much more informal tone”. (SJ3) Several interviewees also admitted that they might need to invest more time into learning how to produce *multimedia content*, such as podcasts, videos, and mixed narrative forms (SJ1-SJ3). The newspaper’s science editor explained some of the different ways they tried to reach new audiences:

We are now trying to break through that wall a bit with, for example, podcasts and turning on the video with the podcast. And we will soon be going into the theater. (...) It is different when hearing someone talk about the pros and cons of mRNA vaccines for say half an hour. And you hear: oh that person knows about it. And oh it's actually just a human being who makes a joke every now and then. Than when someone writes a deadly serious article about it. (SJ3)

Work environment

All interviewees mentioned challenges related to their **work environment**, which can be characterized as the set of conditions under which a science journalist works, including physical, social, and psychological factors. Typical challenges from this theme included issues related to *high workload and time management*, difficulties arising from both the necessity of working with *editors* and the demands of *working alone*, as well as the need to navigate various forms of *competition*. Generally, these challenges corresponded to factors found on several levels, such as the routine, organizational, and institutional level of the Hierarchy of Influences Model (Figure 2).

Deadlines and time pressure are inherent to journalism; news is best consumed when fresh — otherwise it would not be *news* anymore — so journalists are always in a race against the clock. This is not any different for science-reporting journalists, as many spoke about their experiences with *high workloads and time management*. One of the freelancing journalists described “I always have the idea that I am playing catch-up. Things always take longer than you think. Finishing a piece, trying to reach someone, working things out. (...) If you have certain other deadlines, it is complicated.” (SJ1) Another freelancer pointed out that their working capacity is often challenged by the high expectations of their clients, as they ask them to “critically examine an entire paper within a few days”, write a piece about it, and that all while having to “keep an eye on science, *and* popularize it, *and* also [mention] its social relevance.” (SJ2) Not only the clients’ demands can lead to high workloads, also the science journalists’ own desires to take on every job they find interesting can regularly be a burden. Two interviewees, both science editors, mentioned this problem, admitting they often wanted to publish more stories than they had the capacity for (SJ3, SJ5). “The really interesting things often fall by the wayside.” (SJ5)

The freelancing science journalists typically *work alone*, though they frequently interact with the *editors* they write for. Both aspects of their work environment pose their own challenges. One freelancer stated that, compared to journalists working in an editors’ office, self-employed science journalists can get stuck more easily in their writing progress, as they have no colleagues in their vicinity to quickly read through their work and discuss it with (SJ1). Moreover, freelancers might have little insight into the inner workings of news agency editorial offices, which can leave them consistently a step behind in covering new developments. “Newspapers and websites are also

constantly changing their systems (...) And as a freelancer you are all on your own, of course. (...) Things are constantly changing, you don't have any insight into it, you are also in a kind of isolation.” (SJ2) Also the requirements set by editors can be challenging, as another freelancer said “Some have a really tight format for a magazine, (...) they have a really clear idea of what a story should look like. That can sometimes feel a bit obstructive.” (SJ4) Freelancers also have little control over publication of their own work. One interviewee even vented his frustrations about occurrences where editors had adjusted titles, cut away relevant sections from his text, or added in different wordings, without informing him beforehand. (SJ2)

While traditional science journalists used to be the main distributors of science news towards the general public (Dunwoody, 2021), the digital switch of the past decades has enabled new forms of *competition* coming from *free news sources*, putting even more pressure on the capacities of the science journalist. Interviewees mentioned the recent decline in newspaper readership and subscriptions, with more people grabbing their phone for online science news rather than purchasing the paper alternative, “because if you can read it for free somewhere, why would you pay for it?” (SJ5) Another one illustrated:

If you are just interested in high quality news, then people will always make that trade-off of “is [the national newspaper] worth those two cups of coffee at the train station per week, in terms of money, compared to what I can also get for free?” (SJ3)

Interviewees also described that this online competition is largely coming from *science communication practices*. Science communicators are often directly involved in the science itself, be it as a scientist, public information officer, or staff member of a science museum or centre. Participants felt that there was a stark difference between professionals working in science journalism or in science communication; science journalism is a branch within journalism, they explained, ideally attempting to critically evaluate and report science news following journalistic principles, whereas science communication tended to lack these traits. They believed the aim of science communicators is often more concerned with sharing and enthusing people about scientific research, which could lead to conflicts of interest. Furthermore, due to the

wide reach of current social media channels, science communicators can even directly target their audience, bypassing the – generally more sceptical – science journalist. As one of the freelancers says:

Science communication is on the rise. More and more pieces are also being written in science media by communicators and by departments of institutes, communication institutes, or by scientists themselves (...) How very independent, critical is it when scientists [write it] themselves? They actually eliminate you, they want to eliminate the journalist, actually, as an intermediate step to the general public. (...) Those journalists, that's a nuisance, who then ask some difficult questions. They don't need them anymore. (SJ2)

Three interviewees also expressed their worries about the public not being able anymore to distinguish science journalism from science communication, a trend they expect to continue in the coming years (SJ1, SJ2, SJ5). When asked about their expectations for the coming years, one said “A lot of those science [journalists] (...) just work half or more than half-time practically for those [science] institutes. And still call themselves science journalists. Yes, people will soon no longer know the difference.” (SJ2) Also with regard to public funding, some worry about the impact of people not seeing the difference between science journalism and communication:

You are probably wondering as a government, if I give money to the universities to communicate about their research, do I also have to subsidize a medium [science magazine] that communicates about research. They don't see the difference. And the difference is also not very big at times. (SJ5)

Relationships with scientists

Science journalists need to engage frequently with scientists and science institutes, as these are one of their main information sources. Participants indicated that these **relationships with scientists** pose their own unique problems for the journalist, such as *scientists and institutes trying to control their science reporting* and *scientists marketing their own research*. As these challenges correspond to influences from

outside the journalist's organization, they can be classified as institutional level challenges within the Hierarchy of Influences model (Figure 2).

Four participants stated that they had encountered situations where they felt that scientists or science institute communication officers were *attempting to control the contents of their science reporting* (SJ1, SJ2, SJ5, and SJ6). According to their responses, some science institutes are highly concerned with their public image, with communication experts scripting the statements of their scientists and insisting on being present during interviews. The science TV program editor discussed the impact of these measures:

If someone is breathing down your neck all the time, you are not going to ask everything you want to ask in a relaxed way. And certainly also because someone is also listening in, and I have really had people interrupt or that press officers prepare people very much in advance so that they completely shut down, because if a scientist is only concerned with 'I can say this, I am not allowed to say this', you see that immediately. Someone is distracted on camera and you hear someone reading something that has been rehearsed. Someone no longer speaks freely. And I think that's a bad thing. (SJ6)

Also during the writing process, scientists might still try to influence the science journalist's work, as was exemplified by one of the freelancers:

It is quite normal to give access, or to submit a document for inspection to interviewees, or at least their quotes. Yes, scientists can sometimes have a knack for taking that a little too seriously. They then feel like a kind of co-author of the piece, so to speak. And that's a bit annoying or difficult to explain to them like: hey no, in the end it's my name above this article, it's not your piece, and you don't cowrite either. (SJ1)

Another issue mentioned by participants was dealing with *scientists that market their own research*. Three participants mentioned they sometimes had to face scientists and

institutes trying to sell their own work (SJ2, SJ3, and SJ5). One freelancer believed that “as a science journalist you have to be careful not to get involved in that whole technological utopianism or that growth model, that you are not part of that scientific establishment”, in order to maintain your sincerity as an independent journalist. (SJ2) Nonetheless, despite these mentioned problems regarding scientists and institutes, most science journalists assured they had overall efficient and pleasant relationships with their interviewees.

Politics and society

The last overarching challenge theme all participants touched upon were the effects of **politics and society** on their work. They mentioned the impacts of *political and societal developments* on their daily work lives in general and experiencing confrontation when they wrote about *politically sensitive topics*. Especially the issue of dealing with *fake news and misinformation* was often mentioned. Overall, these challenges fall within the social system level of the Hierarchy of Influences model (Figure 2).

When expressing their worries about *political and societal developments*, participants often referenced the growing polarization and distrust against science within society.¹ Some had experienced that scientists were hesitant to speak out publicly about certain topics, due to the sensitivity of the subject. One explained the problems that might arise from this trend:

You now see more and more anonymization. Then someone does not want to be mentioned by his name in the newspaper in order to, yes, not get into trouble with his employer (...) Or students too, for example. They are like, I'd rather not be found forever via Google. And that is complicated, because as a journalist you want to be transparent and verifiable. So by presenting someone anonymously, it makes it difficult to check whether someone has really said something. (SJ1)

¹ Interestingly, according to the European Union's 2024 Eurobarometer survey, the majority of European citizens (83%) still believes that the overall influence of science and technology is positive (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2025).

At least four of the participants were concerned that these trends might continue in the future, further deteriorating the position, and perhaps even the safety, of science journalists. Most had already experienced backlash when reporting on *politically sensitive topics* (SJ1-SJ3, SJ5, and SJ6). One illustrated:

Everything that has to do with nitrogen, RIVM [*Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu*, Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment], everything that affects people personally or politically or where they already have a strong opinion. And then there is a study that says: well it's not the way you think. That's regularly fireworks, yes. (...) Especially during corona, we were sometimes scolded. (SJ3)

Another explained that he felt that as a science journalist “you are expected to be more neutral than other journalists”, which he found difficult when writing about politically sensitive topics such as climate and gender. He stated that in such cases “there is a danger that you will be dismissed as a left-wing, activist journalist and then you will no longer be listened to.” (SJ2)

Lastly, the regular occurrence of *fake news and misinformation* in the media was another challenge participants said they occasionally faced. The science magazine editor illustrated her attempts at dissecting such false science news:

[When I come across misinformation,] I am trying to find out where the story comes from. To look at the source of that misinformation. Usually it's by accident. Either it has been simplified, or someone has said that who did not understand it, and so on. And then the second step is (...) to say, when I write an article, I have to make sure that it is clear. (SJ5)

When asked for their view of the future, many predicted that the dissemination of false scientific information (e.g.: fake news and misinformation) would only intensify over the coming years, and one of the main goals for them would be to maintain the trust from their readers. However, two highlighted, while admitting the dangers of

misinformation, that science journalists must ensure that they will not degrade to a mere fact-check medium, as that would derogate the profession. (SJ1 and SJ5)

Discussion

For this study, six science journalists from the Netherlands and Flanders were interviewed to gather insights in the various challenges that they encounter during their work. Additionally, the interviewees were asked what future challenges they expected to face in the coming ten years. A total of 15 challenges were uncovered that were most frequently mentioned during interviews, which subsequently could be categorized into five overarching themes (see **Interview results**). The following sections will discuss to what extent these challenges for science journalists correspond to those found in previous research, highlighting the most important agreements with and differences from current literature.

Where the resulting challenges agree to previous studies

Financial matters

Consistent with prior research (Dijkstra et al., 2024; Korthagen, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Qusien & Robbins, 2024), all interviewed science journalists reported experiencing financial constraints throughout their work. Especially the decline in paid readership was mentioned as main contributor to lower pay and fewer resources for creating original stories. To get by financially, all three interviewed freelancers took on one or several jobs besides their work as a science journalist. This combining of several jobs appears to be common practice, as a recent global study by Hanitzsch et al. from 2019 showed that one third of the journalists in the Netherlands and one quarter of those in Belgium have a job besides journalism.

High workload and time pressure

Another dominant challenge that emerged both from the literature and the interviews is the high workload and time pressures experienced by freelancing science journalists. As reported by Ashwell (2016), Dijkstra et al. (2024), and Dunwoody (2021), the restructuring of media organizations, with lay-offs of full-time staff and the shift towards more freelance work, has forced remaining science journalists to take on more responsibilities, as self-employed journalists often work for several clients.

Additionally, the study among journalists (Hanitzsch et al., 2019) has also found that the Netherlands has an exceptionally high fraction of freelancers among its journalists, with 37% of the journalists being self-employed, which contrasts greatly with the fact that worldwide only 8.8% of all journalists work on a freelancing basis. Also Belgium has a relatively large share of freelance journalists, as the study showed that 18% of Belgian journalists worked as freelancer. Having more responsibility as a self-employed science journalist was not the only factor that contributed to the high amount of work on their plate. The increase in workload is also intensified by the need to quickly produce content for both print and digital platforms, which results in less time left for in-depth research and original reporting (Dunwoody, 2021). The participants in this study shared these concerns, describing how time pressures occasionally forces them to prioritize speed over depth, sometimes at the expense of critical analysis of scientific publications and overall quality. Although these factors might sometimes be perceived as difficult challenges to deal with, time pressures are also an integral part of the work of the science journalist. As SJ1 put it: “that's just an essential part of the job, those deadlines. And you learn to work with that. I do appreciate them. It also activates you.”

Scientists and science institutes are marketing their research

Furthermore, a notable challenge highlighted by both this and previous studies is the increasing tendency of scientists and research institutes to actively market their own research. In the conducted interviews, several participants reported having to deal with institutes trying to sell themselves, and mentioned they attempted to avoid “listening too hard to the researchers” (SJ2). Studies in New Zealand (Ashwell, 2016) and the United Kingdom (Murcott & Williams, 2013) already noted that the rise of the PR of research institutes has shifted the balance of influences in science communication, where press releases and PR professionals play an increasingly central role in shaping scientific news. This trend might also be at play in the Dutch-speaking media landscape, although further research would be needed to fully confirm this.

Fake news and misinformation

Lastly, the dissemination and proliferation of misinformation about politicized science topics further complicates the daily work tasks of science journalists. Four out of six participants expressed concerns about the increase of misinformation they

encountered during their work, two of which also described the additional burden of fact-checking and distinguishing credible information from so-called ‘fake news’, especially online. These findings align with the observations of West & Bergstrom (2021), who note that the internet has pushed the spread of scientific misinformation to ‘crisis proportions’, mainly because science publications have ‘fallen victim to the ill effects of an attention economy’. In a social media environment, they claim, science communicators are incentivized to hype their research findings, putting the credibility of their claims at risk. Especially during periods where certain scientific topics receive extra attention from the public, such as during the covid-19 pandemic, an overload of science news can increase to fact-checking burden on science journalists (Massarani et al., 2021). However, to what extent these misinformation-debunking practices weigh down on the workload of science journalists in the Netherlands and Flanders is yet to be investigated in further research.

Results not as prevalent in previous studies

Scientists and science institutes attempt to control reporting

This study found that Dutch and Flemish science journalists might occasionally encounter attempts by scientists and institutional PR professionals to direct or control their reporting process. Four interviewees recounted instances in which researchers they had interviewed asked to revise quotes, or even complete articles, before publication, or in which press officers insisted on being present during interviews or scripted the statements of their scientists. Such practices sometimes resulted in tensions in the relationship between the interviewer and the interviewee or were perceived as eroding the journalistic independence of the science reporter.

These findings are only somewhat consistent with international studies, which have recognized the growing influence of Public Relations in science communication. For example, studies by Ashwell (2016) and Murcott & Williams (2013) both showed how journalists, either under time pressure or faced with constrained resources, may become more susceptible towards institutional pressures. This can then lead to ‘churnalism’, where journalists start mindlessly repeating press releases (Davies, 2009; Murcott & Williams, 2013). Additionally, instances of research institutes actively trying to control the written content of scientists have been reported in the South African context (Joubert, 2007). Still, the overall international literature often focuses

on the uncritical copying of PR materials, whereas this study added some nuance to this picture by showing that in the Dutch and Flemish context, there is potentially a more active effort by science institutes to influence the narrative with regard to their organizations, such as direct attempts to control the interview process and contents of the final journalistic piece. These attempts might be a direct result from science institutes themselves being under pressure, as they need to compete for public visibility to ensure research funding for their organizations (Entradas et al., 2020). Consequently, they need to maintain a positive image in the face of the public, possibly leading to science institute executives being more concerned with what a science journalist might want to report about their institute. Though plausible, deeper investigations in this potential correlation are advised for the Dutch and Flemish context.

Growing competition from science communication practices

Half of this study's participants experienced a growing competition from science communication practitioners. Such communicators can be employees from universities, research institutes, and other scientific organizations that promote their research directly to the public. Interviewees described how these communicators are often competent with digital media forms and receive funding from their corresponding organizations, such that they can produce polished, accessible content that reaches audiences through various social media channels. Due to this new competition, the science journalists sometimes felt pressured to change the media form of their work and justify their role as independent intermediaries, rather than amplifiers of institutional messages. Moreover, several participants were concerned that the boundary between science journalism and science communication is blurring in the public eye, which could have impacts on their received funding. Although this new form of competition from science communicators is occasionally mentioned throughout academic (De Semir, 2010; Hayden & Check Hayden, 2018) and non-academic (Callari, 2025; Funk, 2021) literature, no actual research has been done into the impact of science communication practices on the work of science journalists. This topic might be of great interest for future research with regard to the challenges in science journalism since, according to this study, science journalists might feel this trend of increasing science communication efforts threatens their journalistic independence and societal relevance.

Expected future challenges

During the interviews, science journalists were explicitly asked what new challenges they expected to encounter in their profession in the coming ten years. These future expectations have not been investigated before in the Dutch and Flemish context. Among the most frequently mentioned future challenges were the expected impact of generative AI usage on their work, the need to come up with new content forms, and dealing with new political and societal developments such as polarization and fake news. Strikingly, all challenges they expected to develop in the future were all problems they already encounter nowadays. This result is in accordance with what is known about how expectations are formed, as people are generally prone to base their expectations for the future on their own personal local circumstances and experiences (Curtin, 2022).

For example, AI has been a hot topic in the public debate since the launch of OpenAI's ChatGPT in November 2022. Sentiments about this new AI tool have been mixed, ranging from optimism about its possible applications to concerns about the technology being misused or making various jobs redundant (Ng & Chow, 2024). A recent study among German science journalists focused solely on expectations with regard to generative AI and found that most hope that these tools will alleviate the workload, although some are also concerned that their work could be taken over entirely (Guenther et al., 2025). It is not surprising that comparable expectations have also reached the minds of Dutch and Flemish science journalists, explaining the abundant mentioning of this theme in this study.

Similarly, anxiety about potential future developments in politics is most likely fueled by current developments in the international and national political landscape that impact science journalism. It should be noted that in particular the TV program editor was concerned with current and future politics, as her employer, a public broadcaster, was announced to be discontinued due to governmental budget cuts only a week before our interview. Obviously, this unfortunate event heavily impacted her view on the (near) future prospects for her job, explaining her fixation on this subject.

All in all, given that the next decade is yet to pass, future research must elicit the actual challenges that science journalists will encounter as the Dutch and Flemish media landscape continues to evolve.

Challenges from previous studies not found in this study

Interestingly, some challenges for science journalism that were regularly mentioned in international literature did not come forward as prominently during the interviews. Frequently occurring challenges in literature that were not found in this study were that of science journalists being forced to use preprints and PR materials (Ashwell, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Massarani et al., 2021; Murcott & Williams, 2013), having a job that is predominantly desk-bound (Ashwell, 2016; Massarani et al., 2021; Qusien & Robbins, 2024), and having to deal with scientists that are not available or not able to speak at an understandable level for the journalist (Ashwell, 2016; Maiden et al., 2020; Nguyen & Tran, 2019; Qusien & Robbins, 2024). These discrepancies between this and other studies can have various explanations.

Firstly, Ashwell (2016) already observed that smaller, local news agencies are more prone to literally copy preprints and press releases from science institutes than their established national counterparts, as they generally have less resources to write original stories. However, science journalists interviewed for this study mainly write for bigger news agencies. Hence, it is to be expected that these participants experience less difficulties with trying to write original stories, as they generally have sufficient time and resources.

The second challenge not mentioned by participants was that of the work being desk-bound. Literature suggests that this problem was mostly occurring during the covid-19 crisis (Massarani et al., 2021) and in countries in the Global South (Qusien & Robbins, 2024). Both conditions did not apply for this study's participants, clarifying why no one raised this issue. Likewise, it was often in Global South nations that science journalists were reported to not be able to reach or sufficiently follow the statements of interviewed researchers (Nguyen & Tran, 2019; Qusien & Robbins, 2024). Accordingly, none of the interviewees, with the exception of one participant (SJ6), mentioned experiencing difficulties in achieving the same level of understanding as the researchers they interviewed.

Limitations and future research

While this research has elicited valuable insights into the various challenges that science journalists face in the Netherlands and Flanders, some limitations should be mentioned to contextualize the findings of this study.

To start, the generalizability of these findings are limited by the relatively small sample size ($N = 6$). As all results of this research relied on in-depth interviews with only a small group of science journalists, the experienced challenges reported may not fully represent the overall population of science journalists in these countries. Furthermore, although it was attempted to sample a random selection of science journalists in the region, some snowball sampling could have occurred, such as in the case of at least one participant (SJ5), who was recruited after the recommendation of another participant (SJ2). This use of snowball sampling may have introduced bias towards participants with certain backgrounds and political views, possibly leading to an underrepresentation of other viewpoints within science journalism.

Secondly, there might be more challenges and themes that have remained unmentioned in this study. This potential absence of certain challenges may not be attributed to their irrelevance, but rather to the fact that the questions asked during the interview did not evoke participants to give these as answers. It was attempted to set up the interview guide as unbiased towards certain themes as possible by only asking about the different levels as defined in the Hierarchy of Influences model (Reese & Shoemaker, 2016). Still, questions could have influenced which themes were explored during the interviews and which not.

Thirdly, another limitation could be that this study solely focused on challenges as experienced by science journalists, excluding other stakeholders such as scientists and PR professionals. This restriction may have resulted in an understanding of challenges that was only partial or skewed, since the views of the people who interact with science journalists were not represented. However, the relationships of these other parties, such as scientists, with media practitioners have been studied extensively (de Jong & Dijkstra, 2022), underscoring the argument that it was sufficient for this study to only include the perspective of science journalists.

Lastly, it might be of interest to briefly reflect on the use of Reese & Shoemaker's Hierarchy of Influences model (2016) as theoretical framework for this study. This framework provided a helpful structure for thinking about the different levels a challenge can occur on (individual, routine, organizational, institutional, and societal) and for prompting new discussions during the interviews. Nonetheless, the multifaceted and often overlapping nature of these challenges meant that they were not always neatly categorized into one of the levels of the model. Hence, the model was

only used in a broad way to start thinking about the challenges, and not for precise analysis and categorization of the resulting challenges.

Overall, these limitations suggest that the results of this study should be interpreted cautiously, but also point to possible directions for future research. New studies investigating the challenges for science journalists could benefit from a larger and more diverse sample. To achieve this, a national survey could be conducted in both the Netherlands and Flanders that aims to target all science journalists working in this region, or at least a significant part of those. By providing participants with the challenges that appeared in this study and in other studies, they could fill in which they experience as well and which they do not experience. Quantitative results from such a future study could provide a strong fundament to base new policies on that aid Dutch and Flemish science journalists in overcoming the challenges they face during their work.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to explore the challenges currently faced by science journalists in the Netherlands and Flanders, as well as the challenges they foresee for the coming decade. By conducting semi-structured interviews with six science journalism professionals, this research provides a first overview of the various issues that are connected to this field.

After analysis of the interviews, a total of five overarching challenge themes were found to be experienced by Dutch and Flemish science journalists: **Economic security**, **Content**, **Work environment**, **Relationships with scientists**, and **Politics and society**. Some of the specific challenges within these themes were also abundant in international literature, such as problems with generating *income*, *high workloads* and *increased time pressures*, dealing with *science institutes that market their own research*, and the growing concerns about *misinformation*. However, the interviews also revealed distinctive challenges that are not yet prominently described by previous studies; they occasionally experienced *science institutes and scientists trying to control their work* and reported a *growing competition from science communicators*.

Importantly, this research showed that science journalists' expectations about the future are grounded in developments that are already happening today. From the *rise*

of *generative AI* to the need to come up with *new ways of content production*, and with concerns about *new political developments*, participating journalists anticipate for the coming ten years a media landscape that will become more demanding for their profession.

All in all, with the pressure growing on both science and journalism, reaffirming the role of the independent and critical science journalist has become more essential than ever before. This research has contributed to this goal by shining a light on the current challenges and future concerns of those working in the ever-evolving field of science journalism in the Netherlands and Flanders. Hopefully, the results have laid the groundwork for the development of further support to preserve the livelihood security and public relevance of science journalists.

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AI statement: This research follows the Leiden University Guidelines for use of AI in research and education. In some cases, ChatGPT (GPT-4) was used to help reformulate and/or restructure sentences (see **Example 1 and 2**). Perplexity Search Pro was used to help understand the Hierarchy of Influences model by summarizing the corresponding publications, accelerating my learning process.

Example 1 (ChatGPT) prompt: ‘Rewrite “The freelancing science journalists mostly work alone, with frequent interactions with the editors they write for.”’

Example 1 answer ChatGPT: ‘Freelance science journalists typically work independently, though they often engage in regular communication with the editors they write for.’

Final sentence example 1 in report: The freelancing science journalists typically *work alone*, though they frequently interact with the *editors* they write for.

Example 2 (ChatGPT) prompt: ‘Interviewees mentioned the recent decrease in newspaper readership and subscriptions, with more people grabbing their phone for online science news than a paper alternative that needs to be paid for. <how would you rewrite this sentence academically?’

Example 2 answer ChatGPT: ‘Interviewees noted a recent decline in newspaper readership and subscriptions, attributing it to a growing preference for accessing science news online via mobile devices, rather than purchasing traditional print newspapers.’

Final sentence example 2 in report: Interviewees mentioned the recent decline in newspaper readership and subscriptions, with more people grabbing their phone for online science news rather than purchasing the paper alternative.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Informed consent form

You wish to participate in our research “*Exploring the challenges faced by science journalists in the Dutch and Flemish media landscape*”. Our research seeks to identify the current and future challenges that Dutch and Flemish science journalists (might) face during their work.

To perform our research, we need to process your personal data. To be able to lawfully process your data for this research, we hereby ask for your consent. This document will explain what personal data we need, why we need it, and what your rights regarding your personal data are.

We assure you that we process your data carefully and in accordance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring the security and confidentiality of your information. If possible, we’ll pseudonymize or anonymize data.

Personal data

In the table below, you will find a list of the types of personal data we will be processing for this research, alongside with our purpose for doing so.

Types of data	Purpose of processing
Name, contact details	Contact
Signature	Consent form
Gender, nationality and occupation	Demographic information for study
Challenges you experienced during your work/you expect to experience in the future	Core data for study
Recording of interview	For transcription

All your data will be pseudonymized as much as possible. E.g. you will be referred to as SJ1 (Science journalist 1) in the final paper, not by name.

Storage and deletion

When our research is completed, we will delete all recordings. We will not publish your name and contact details. We will remove your data as soon as we are done analyzing it. The personal data will be archived up until one month after the conclusion of the study. We are bound to do so following the Code of Conduct for Research Integrity of Leiden University. After the retention period, the personal data will be deleted. All appropriate technical, and organizational, measures to protect and secure the data, will be taken.

Future data use

We will not be using your personal data in the future.

Your rights

You have certain right regarding your personal data which is processed for this research project. These rights derive from the General Data Protection Regulation.

The right of access: You have the right to see what kind of personal data we process about you.

The right of rectification: You have the right to rectify (partially) incorrect or incomplete personal data.

The right to erasure: You have the right to request the permanent deletion of all the personal data we processed of you.

The right to restrict processing: You have the right to restrict the processing of your personal data. Your data will temporarily only be stored and not processed any further. This right is of importance when you have, for example, requested rectification of the personal data.

The right to data portability: You have the right to move, copy, or transfer personal data from one data controller to another, in a safe and secure way, in a commonly used and machine-readable format. This right is used to enable easy transfer between IT-providers for example. In the context of this research this right is not of importance.

The right to withdraw consent: You have the right to withdraw the given consent at any time. The personal data will not be processed any further and will be deleted. If the data is already anonymized deletion will not be possible.

Feel free to contact the researcher should you have any questions about the research or if you wish to invoke your rights by emailing d.roodbol@umail.leidenuniv.nl with a short message to accompany your request. If we are unable to fulfill your request, our Privacy Officers will get in touch with you.

Contact details

Universiteit Leiden

Science Communication and Society

Student researcher: Duuk Roodbol (d.roodbol@umail.leidenuniv.nl)

Supervisor: Pedro Russo (russo@strw.leidenuniv.nl)

Data Protection Officer

Any questions about the processing of your data may also be addressed to the Data Protection Officer of Leiden University. The Data Protection Officer can be contacted via

privacy@bb.leidenuniv.nl.

Complaints

If you have any complaints about this research, you can turn to the secretary of the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Humanities of Leiden University, Myrte Vos

(ethics@hum.leidenuniv.nl).

If you are unhappy with the way Leiden University has handled the processing of your data, you can state your complaint with the Data Protection Officer. If you are unhappy with the way Leiden University has handled your complaint, you can file a complaint with the Supervisory Authority, the [Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens](#).

Please check the boxes that apply.

Below you may confirm that you have understood this document and consent to its content.

- I consent to the use of my personal data for the purposes outlined in this consent form.

Your information:

Name

Date and location

Signature

Appendix 2: Interview guide

This interview guide is a translation of the original Dutch interview guide.

What to say and ask	Notes
<p>Thank you for participating in the interview.</p> <p><Introduce myself: Student Life sciences, specialize in science communication. In September, I will do an internship at the science editorial office of the Volkskrant. But first research among science journalists></p> <p>That's how I found you > you area science journalist</p> <p>I have some questions for you later about your work and about the challenges you encounter within your work. I am also curious about what new challenges you expect to encounter within your field of work for the next ten years.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there a time when they really want to be done with the interview? • Zoom: Mention that after 40 min of meeting ends > same link login if we are not done yet. <p><check whether informed consent has been completed and start recording.></p>	Introduction
<p>1. Can you tell me what kind of work you do?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which tasks? • How long already? • Employers? • Freelancer? 	Icebreaker
<p>2. If you look at your work in science journalism, what kind of challenges do you face?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personally/you as an individual/your (educational) background? • Daily tasks/obligations/routine? • Employer/client/your organization? • Other organization/agencies you deal with? • Challenges you experience from society/government? 	Ask for experiences!
<p>3. When you look ahead to the coming years, do you expect new challenges to arise for you as a science journalist?</p> <p>Yes: Which ones?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal change? • Changes in work tasks? • Change in organization/clients? • From society/government? <p>No: Why not?</p>	Question: based on what experiences do they expect this?
<p>4. Is there anything else we haven't talked about yet that you would like to mention?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anything else you want to say something about? 	Open comment
<p>Completion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask what gender they want to be referred to by • Ask if they want to receive transcript • Ask if they would like to receive a research report in the end 	

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Let me know that they can always email me if they have any questions about the research and their data• Thank you for participating | |
|--|--|

Appendix 3: Codebook

All sections in the transcript that have a comment attached should be coded with two codes: *Code1: Challenges* (C1-C23) and *Code2: Moment of challenge* (M1-M3). All codes are explained + exemplified in the next part of this document. Codes can be added to a highlighted section by going to the corresponding comment and replying with **1, and only 1, code from Code1 and 1 code from Code2, like this: Cx, My.**

SJ = Science journalist.

Research questions of this research internship:

Research question 1:

*What are the challenges Dutch and Flemish science journalists are **currently** facing during their work?*

Research question 2:

*What **new** challenges Dutch and Flemish science journalists expect to be facing during their work **within the coming ten years**?*

Overview codes

Code1: Challenge	Code2: Moment of challenge
C1: Competition from other news sources	M1: Current challenge
C2: Competition from science communication	M2: Future challenge
C3: Creative/engaging content	M3: Both current and future challenge
C4: Explaining science	
C5: Selecting topics	
C6: Credibility	
C7: Fake news/misinformation	
C8: Impact AI	
C9: Multimedia content	
C10: Income	
C11: Less work/clients available	
C12: Working alone	
C13: Scientific expertise	
C14: Sincerity	
C15: Political/societal developments	
C16: Politically sensitive topics	
C17: Science journalism seen as unimportant	
C18: Editors	
C19: Obtaining data	
C20: Politicians	
C21: Scientists marketing research	
C22: Scientists/science institutes	
C23: Workload and time management	

Explanations Code1: Challenges

One, and only one, of the following 23 codes is applied to every sections where the SJ talks about one of the challenges they currently encounter or expect to encounter in the future during their work. **The code signifies what kind of challenge the SJ talks about.**

Theme1: Competition

C1: Competition from other news sources

Code used when SJ talks about the competition they experience from other news sources. NOT competition from science communicators.

Examples:

- Competition from free/online news sources.
- Competition from sources that receive governmental funding.

C2: Competition from science communication

Code used when SJ talks about the competition they experience from science communication.

Examples:

- Science institute members (be it a scientist, science communicator, press officer, science museums etc.) directly sharing science news with audiences, thereby bypassing science journalists.
- Audiences and/or interviewees not being able to see the difference between science journalism and science communication.
- Science communication getting more funding.
- Science institutes wanting to eliminate science journalists as intermediaries in the distribution of science news.
- Science journalists becoming science communicators themselves.

Theme2: Content

C3: Creative/engaging content

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of making content in more creative and engaging ways. NOT used when talking about the format of the content (video/podcast/etc.).

Examples:

- Creating content that people like to read.

- Involving more the human/creative aspect in content.
- Creating more visually pleasing content.
- Having an attractive writing style.
- Using more informal words.

C4: Explaining science

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of clearly explaining science topics to the general public.

Examples:

- Science becoming more complex and therefore harder to explain.
- It is hard to explain the limitations of research to the general public.

C5: Selecting topics

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge they encounter in trying to select topics to report about.

Examples:

- Choosing what to and what not to report.
- Coming up with topics.

Theme3: Credibility

C6: Credibility

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of proving their credibility as a medium or individual to their audience. NOT used when talking about fake news and misinformation in general.

Examples:

- Words used as reliability/credibility/trustworthy **when speaking about themselves.**
- Being transparent as medium.
- Convincing audiences that their news is reliable.

C7: Fake news/misinformation

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of dealing with fake news and/or misinformation. NOT when talking about proving their own credibility to their audience.

Examples:

- Not knowing what to believe.
- Dealing with fake news and misinformation while performing research for a piece.
- Debunking fake news and misinformation as SJ.

Theme4: Digital environments

C8: Impact AI

Code used when SJ talks about the impacts of AI usage on their work.

Examples:

- Talking about impact AI/artificial intelligence/automatically generated content in general.
- What can be done more easily with AI.
- Becoming less useful due to AI.

C9: Multimedia content

Code used when SJ talks about the challenges due to the rising demand for multimedia content. So only applies to the format of the content (video/podcast/written/etc.), NOT to the content itself.

Examples:

- Feeling the need to make more content in the form of podcasts/videos/etc. (more than just writing).
- Not having the technical skills to make such content.

Theme5: Economic security

C10: Income

Code used when SJ talks about not being able to pay/earn enough money and/or about ways to earn more money. NOT used when talking about combining different jobs without mentioning the financial aspect/reason for it.

Examples:

- Words used as: income/pay/salary/money

- Being able to earn more (in combination) with another job.
- Less budget/fundings available.

C11: Less work/clients available

Code used when SJ talks about less work and/or clients being available. NOT used when talking about challenges they have with clients they do have.

Examples:

- Words like 'not enough market', 'little space', 'few job opportunities/clients', 'fewer magazines', etc.
- Job security/jobs disappearing.
- Uncertainties in assignments.

Theme6: Freelancing

C12: Working alone

Code used when SJ talks about the challenges they encounter due to working alone/without a team as freelancer.

Examples:

- Not being involved in what happens at the editorial office.
- Financial disadvantages due to being a freelancer/self-employed.

Theme7: Personal knowledge and attitude

C13: Scientific expertise

Code used when SJ talks about feeling not having enough scientific expertise/knowledge for their job.

Examples:

- Not having the right background studies.
- Having difficulty knowing something about everything.

C14: Sincerity

Code used when SJ talks about maintaining sincerity as a journalist.

Examples:

- About the importance of not losing sincerity.

Theme8: Politics and society

C15: Political/societal developments

Code used when SJ talks about political and/or societal developments that harm their role/work as SJ. NOT used when talking about difficulties with reporting about politically sensitive topics.

Examples:

- Talking about politics in general.
- About the impact of polarization
- Scientists not wanting their name published due to political/societal controversy
- Political figures saying (science) journalists are useless/overpaid.
- Public funding cuts
- Hate/violence against journalists.

C16: Politically sensitive topics

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of reporting about politically sensitive topics. So really when the content they report about is politically controversial. NOT used when talking about political developments in general.

Examples:

- Difficulties with writing about topics such as corona, climate, etc.
- Other people using your written work for their own arguments.
- Difficulties in not involving your own political views too much/remaining objective.
- Interviewees having different political views.
- Self-censorship.

C17: Science journalism seen as unimportant

Code used when SJ talks about people/society seeing science journalism as unimportant as compared to other disciplines.

Examples:

- Not being popular/taken seriously.
- Science journalism departments being scrapped.

Theme9: Stakeholder relationships

C18: Editors

Code used when SJ talks about the challenges they encounter in their relationships with editors they work with. **NOT** used when talking about difficulties in finding clients.

Examples:

- Editors controlling/editing the texts.
- Editors already having certain topics in their own portfolio.

C19: Obtaining data

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of obtaining data from external parties.

Examples:

- Access to data not easy.
- Data difficult to decipher.

C20: Politicians

Code used when SJ talks about the challenges they encounter in their relationships with politicians. **NOT** used when talking about general political or societal developments,

Examples:

- Politicians trying to use SJs for their own gain.

C21: Scientists marketing research

Code used when SJ talks about the challenge of dealing with scientists/institutes that try to sell/market their own research to science journalists. NB so really concerning scientists that reach out to the SJ trying to promote their own work. **NOT** used when talking about problems in the work relationship with scientists/institutes.

Examples:

- Not going along too quickly with the narrative of a scientist.
- Words as: selling, promoting, advertising, marketing etc.

- Science conducted by stakeholders of the outcomes.

C22: Scientists/science institutes

Code used when SJ talks about the challenges they encounter in their relationships with scientists and/or science institutes they work with. **NOT** used when talking about scientists/institutes taking on the role of science communicator and/or scientists selling their own research.

Examples:

- Words used as: scientists, press/information officers, experts, interviewees (in most cases)
- Scientists wanting to alter texts.

Theme10: Workload and time management

C23: Workload and time management

Code used when SJ talks about the challenges that come with a high workload and time management.

Examples:

- Difficulties with deadlines, limited work time/work capacity, high expectations, etc.
- Choosing what pieces to prioritize.

Explanations Code2: Moment of challenge

One of the following 3 codes is applied to every sections where the SJ talks about one of the challenges they currently encounter or expect to encounter in the future during their work. **The code signifies whether they are talking about a current challenge, an expected future challenge, or both.**

M1: Current challenge

Code used when SJ mentions a challenge that they encounter now/in the present/have encountered.

Examples:

- Talking in present tense/about the present.
- Talking in past tense/about past.
- Direct answer to a question about their current situation.

M2: Future challenge

Code used when SJ mentions a challenge that they expect to encounter in the future.

Examples:

- Talking in future tense (will + inf.)/about the future.
- Talking about what might be (might/may (become)), what they expect can happen.
- Direct answer to a question about their expectations for the coming 10 years.
- Talking about something not being the case at the moment (yet).
- Expectations/advice for what they should start doing.

M3: Both current and future challenge

Code used when SJ mentions a challenge that they encounter currently and expect to encounter in the future.

Examples:

- Talking about something staying the same or getting worse over the years (**remains/is becoming more/is on the rise/increasingly/etc.**)
- Combining present and future tense.
- Mentioning something **already/again** being the case +expectations that it stays that way.